

THE USE OF CLASSIC STYLES IN MODERN FASHION

Amonova Zarifa Usmonovna

Navoiy state pedagogical institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7876315>

Abstract. *This article provides information about the classic style and mini styles in design art.*

Keywords: *clothing, man, woman, art, style, classic, black, dress, pants, suits, contrast, haute couture, fabric, decoration.*

Clothes have different functions or tasks. Clothing should protect the human body. In addition, clothes have an information function, that is, an informative function. Clothing has always played the role of a sign of a person's social class and profession. It was possible to get an idea of a person's profession by looking at how he was dressed. For example, in Europe, the mantle of a judge is not like an officer's uniform. In the peoples of Central Asia, the color and decoration of clothes, as well as their length and length, gave information about whether a woman was married or not, to which caste she belonged, and to which region she was from.

Clothing should be treated not only as a consumer product, but as a work of practical art. An example of this is the beautiful examples of historical and traditional clothes collected in various museums of the world.

Style is an artistic language defined by a unique social and economic structure of history and era. Style shows the composition and form of all components of artistic creation, and the pictorial uniqueness of the overall embodiment of personality and era.

Classic style (classic style, classic costume, classic fashion) - there are such clothes that, despite the change of human taste, requirements, interests, and habits, they remain unchanged in a certain sense. The British costume, which belongs to the classic fashion and is sometimes even called the classic fashion, is one of those clothes. The public will always consider him to be wonderful, excellent, and an example. The women's suit and "little black dress" offered by the French fashion designer Gabriel Chanel are among such clothes.

Classic style, simplicity of lines, laconic cut. Clothes in this style are attractive due to their high quality and quality of materials. Achromatic colors or pastel shades prevail. This is the most pleasant style, everything in it is very moderate. Length, width, volume and proportions are always average, familiar to the eye. A classic dress will live long in fashion because it is refined, aesthetically pleasing, elegant and perfect.

The English costume, which appeared in the 18th century, is the opposite of the luxurious and uncomfortable clothing of men in the French Versailles fashion. The French at that time wore silk caftans and short pants called culottes. And the British, as mentioned above, offered durable and comfortable clothing, derived from the clothing of horse riders, as everyday wear. This outfit consisted of a frock coat (waistcoat with a long hem at the back) worn over a redingot (long coat), narrow trousers (trousers) and boots topped with reversible double-breasted boots. This new men's dress also affected women's clothing: women began to wear this costume, which they called the English costume, in the 80s of the 19th century. It included a straight skirt (with or without pleats) and a lined jacket. The jacket had a stand-up collar on the neck and a turn-down collar on the chest. The fabric used for this men's and women's clothing is plain, with subtle stripes or checks, and has

a soft color - movut, and later it was named custom-made fabric or custom-made movut. This dress was usually sewn by special tailors. Soon, as it became popular, ready-made clothing workshops appeared.

Classic style is one of the styles and includes small styles.

1. Cage style of fabric. The suit is made of checkered fabrics in a classic style, the clothes are sophisticated, the aesthetic is flawless, and it is perfect.

2. Chanel style. Gabriel Chanel is a French fashion designer who changed the style of women's clothing on this planet. The created clothes were distinguished by comfortable and high-quality restoration. A little black dress has become a great gift for all women. The goal was to create a versatile dress at the same time. Until then, black color was considered a sign of sadness. But the elegant item presented in a new look quickly gained popularity among fashionistas.

3. Style of English suit. An English suit is a type of clothing that, as a general concept, symbolizes business and seriousness in terms of color and shape. It appeared in the 18th century in contrast to the luxurious and uncomfortable clothing of men in the Versailles fashion of the French.

4. Minimalizm style. Minimalism style pantsuits, belts or simple shirts with long sleeves, t-shirts, straight skirts and t-shirts will always be the main here. Familiar fabrics are soft wool, knitwear, cotton, silk, satin and leather.

The classic style is recognized by the whole world and never goes out of style, it is repeated again and again. Classic Haute Couture dresses are created and presented to the public in a single copy by designers. Classic costume composition - equality, similarity and contrast; symmetry and asymmetry; proportions, rhythm, compositional center; tools such as color are aggregates. These elements that make up the costume form a whole that reflects a certain idea, an artistic image.

"Haute Couture" (French: "Haute-couture" - in the sense of high-level tailoring or high-art tailoring) - currently used in the sense of "high fashion" means the creation of clothes of the highest class level. Clothes belonging to this class or category are made in a single copy, they are mostly sewn by hand. Not only the process of making clothes, but also the fabric or material, types of decorations are done by hand and are unique and unrepeatable.

REFERENCES

1. F.Otakhonova. Modern dress modelling. Guide-book, Tashkent – 2013.
2. F.Otakhonova. Design project. Guide-book. – Tashkent-2018
3. Kh.Komilova, U.Vohidova. Designing. Guide-book. – Tashkent-2017.
4. Гусейнов Г.М. Ермилова В.В. Композиция костюма. Т.2003.
5. Kh.Kamilova, N.Xamrayeva. "Construction of sewing items": a textbook for higher educational institutions. - Tashkent: 2011. - 400 p.